

base type of condensation to give the cyclic products 4a and 4b, respectively. In order to adduce support to this proposed mechanism 5 has been synthesised by the condensation of *N*-phenacylpyridinium bromide and 1 to compare the spectral data. The yellow merocyanine (5) absorbs at 387 nm which is very close to λ_{max} value shown by the compounds 3a and 3b.

This confirms the fact that the condensation (Scheme 1) proceeds through the formation of the merocyanines 3a and 3b. We have also synthesised 4b by the condensations of 1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (6) with 1 (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The compounds isolated from both the methods (Schemes 1 and 2) compare well and so confirms the structures of 4a and 4b.

In order to evaluate the influence of quaternising group on absorption, various dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 1 with *N*-methyl- and *N*-phenacyl-quaternary heterocyclic compounds (7 and 9) in alcohol. The monoazadimethines (8) derived from 7 absorb at 430-575 nm, whereas the dyes (10) obtained from 9 absorb at 380-390 nm.

The compound 1 can condense with 9 either with 2-methyl group or with the methylene group of phenacyl moiety. If the condensation would have occurred with the methyl group λ_{max} would have occurred in the region where the dyes derived from 7 absorb. Since the dyes show absorption in a different region much below those obtained from 7 it clearly indicates that the condensation has occurred with the methylene group. This also looks logical, since the methylene group is capable of forming an ylide system stabilised by the presence of the C=O group. No peak was also obtained around 430 nm region indicating exclusive condensation with the methylene group. Moreover, the absorption of 10 compares very well with that of 5. Hence, the course of the reaction as proposed in Scheme 1 is clearly proved. The phenacyl moiety as a quaternising agent does not have substantial influence on absorption but because of the presence of C=O group in it, an *in situ* condensation occurs leading to increase of conjugation.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The uv spectra were taken in a Toshniwal RL 02 spectrophotometer and the ir spectra in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. 1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (6) was also synthesised by the method of Pandler and Blewitt³.

1-Aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (1) : 1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (1.94 g) was dissolved in water and cooled in ice-bath. A mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and aniline was prepared. The hydrochloride so obtained was dissolved in water and an aqueous solution of excess of sodium nitrite was added to it on ice-bath. The whole mixture was then added to the solution of azapyrrocolinium bromide in an ice-bath and stirred with a magnetic stirrer for 0.5 h. The precipitate was filtered and chromatographed over alumina when a crystalline green compound was

obtained as a major product. The purity of the compound was checked by tlc with benzene as the developer ($R_f=0.35$), (80%), m.p. 160° (Found : C, 69.45; H, 4.15; N, 18.95, $C_{13}H_9N_3O$ requires C, 69.6; H, 4.0; N, 18.83%).

Similarly when 1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (1.94 g) was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium nitrite in excess, a green compound was precipitated. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and crystallised with alcohol-water mixture, (80%), m.p. and m.m.p. 160° (Found : C, 69.64; H, 4.17; N, 18.947%); identified to be the nitroso compound, λ_{max} 430 nm.

Quaternisation : 2-Methyl heterocyclic compounds were quaternised by heating with methyl iodide in sealed tube at 100° for 48 h. The methiodides were washed with ether and crystallised from alcohol.

The *N*-phenacyl quaternary salts were synthesised by condensation of the bases with phenacyl bromide. *N*-Phenacyl-2-aminopyridinium bromide (65%), m.p. 118° (Found : Br, 26.98. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2OBr$ requires Br, 27.3%); *N*-phenacylpyridinium bromide (65%), m.p. 112° (Found : Br, 27.3. $C_{13}H_{12}NOBr$ requires Br, 27.78%); *N*-phenacyl-2-methylpyridinium bromide (80%), m.p. 196° (Found : Br, 27.3. $C_{14}H_{14}NOBr$ requires Br, 27.39%).

N-[ω -(1-aza-2-phenyl pyrrocolyl-3-imino)phenacyl]-2-methylpyridinium bromide (3a) : *N*-Phenacyl-2-methylpyridinium bromide (0.292 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in absolute ethanol were heated over a water-bath for 2 h. After removal of the solvent the dye was precipitated by adding ether, and purified by alternate dissolution and reprecipitation in acetone and ether, respectively. It was then dried *in vacuo* (65%), m.p. 110° (Found : C, 64.38; H, 3.76; N, 11.59. $C_{26}H_{19}N_4OBr$ requires C, 64.59; H, 3.93; N, 11.66%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 390 nm. Other compounds (10) were prepared by the same method from different *N*-phenacyl-2-methyl heterocyclic compounds and their m.p., analytical data and λ_{max} values have been reported in Table 1.

N-[ω -(1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocolyl-3-imino)phenacyl]-2-aminopyridinium bromide (3b) : It was prepared

from *N*-phenacyl-2-aminopyridinium bromide (0.293 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in absolute ethanol, (60%), m.p. 150° (Found : C, 62.03; H, 3.68; N, 14.52. $C_{25}H_{18}N_5OBr$ requires C, 61.97; H, 3.72; N, 14.46%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 393 nm.

Bis(1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocoline)azamethincyanine bromide (4b) : *Method A* : It was prepared from *N*-phenacyl-2-aminopyridinium bromide (0.293 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in acetic anhydride, (60%) m.p. 195° (Found : C, 64.89; H, 3.71; N, 14.36. $C_{26}H_{18}N_5Br$ requires C, 65.00; H, 3.75; N, 14.58%); λ_{max} (Ac_2O) 650 nm.

Method B : It was prepared from 1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (0.195 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in acetic anhydride after refluxing for 5 h, (50%), m.p. and m.m.p. 195° (Found C, 64.92; H, 3.79; N, 14.40. $C_{26}H_{18}N_5Br$ requires C, 65.00; H, 3.75; N, 14.58%); λ_{max} (Ac_2O) 650 nm.

(1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocoline) (2-phenylpyrrocoline)-azamethincyanine bromide (4a) : It was prepared from *N*-phenacyl-2-methylpyrrocolinium bromide (0.292 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in acetic anhydride, (60%), m.p. 206° (Found : C, 62.24; H, 3.48; N, 11.71. $C_{28}H_{17}N_4Br$ requires C, 62.37; H, 3.53; N, 11.64%); λ_{max} (Ac_2O) 620 nm.

N-[ω -(1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolyl-3-imino)phenacyl]-pyridinium bromide (5) : It was prepared from *N*-phenacylpyridinium bromide (0.278 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in alcohol, (70%), m.p. 130° (Found : C, 64.47; H, 4.02; N, 11.46. $C_{26}H_{16}N_4OBr$ requires C, 64.6; H, 3.93; N, 11.59%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 387 nm.

(1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocoline)(*N*-methylpyridine) monoazadimethincyanine iodide (8). It was prepared from *N*-methyl-2-methylpyridinium iodide (0.235 g) and 1-aza-3-nitroso-2-phenylpyrrocoline (0.223 g) in alcohol, (65%), m.p. 135° (Found : C, 54.29; H, 3.93; N, 12.58. $C_{26}H_{18}N_4I$ requires C, 54.42; H, 4.08; N, 12.70%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 430 nm. Other monoazadimethincyanines were synthesised by the same method from different *N*-methyl-2-methyl heterocyclic compounds and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 10

Nature of A	M.p. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} nm	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
Benzothiazole	125	60	390	$C_{22}H_{11}N_4SOBr$	62.78 (62.90)	3.58 (3.79)	10.06 (10.12)
4-Ph-thiazole	140	65	410	$C_{21}H_{11}N_4SOBr$	63.98 (64.20)	3.82 (3.97)	9.46 (9.67)
Benzoxazole	125	65	390	$C_{22}H_{11}N_4O_2Br$	64.71 (64.80)	3.87 (3.91)	10.33 (10.42)
Quinoline	137	60	387	$C_{21}H_{11}NOBr$	67.89 (68.00)	4.11 (4.20)	10.08 (10.23)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 8

Nature of A	M p. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} nm	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
Benzothiazole	130	60	540	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	53.19 (53.22)	3.51 (3.63)	11.32 (11.43)
Benzoxazole	125	60	490	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	54.89 (55.00)	3.42 (3.54)	11.70 (11.66)
Quinoline	120	65	575	C ₁₀ H ₉ N	28.64 (28.77)	3.75 (3.87)	11.28 (11.43)

nitrosoazapyrrocoline. Their m.p analytical data and λ_{max} values have been reported in (Table 2).

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